

Military Families' Attachment to the Royal Guards Community of Dusit District, Bangkok Metropolitan

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I. INTRODUCTION

Abstract—The objective of this research is to study the people's level of participation in activities of the community, their satisfaction towards the community, the attachment they have to the community, factors that influence the attachment, as well as the characteristics of the relationships of military families' of the Royal Guards community of Dusit District. The method used was non-probability sampling by quota sampling according to people's age. The determined age group was 18 years or older.

One set of a sample group was done per family. The questionnaires were conducted by 287 people. Snowball sampling was also used by interviewing people of the community, starting from the Royal Guards Community's leader, then by 20 of the community's well-respected persons. The data was analyzed by using descriptive statistics, such as arithmetic mean and standard deviation, as well as by inferential statistics, such as Independent - Samples T test (T-test), One-Way ANOVA (F-test), Chi-Square. Descriptive analysis according to the structure of the interview content was also used. The results of the research is that the participation of the population in the Royal Guards Community in various activities is at a medium level, with the average participation level during Mother's and Father's Days. The people's general level of satisfaction towards the premises of the Royal Guards Community is at the highest level.

The people were most satisfied with the transportation within the community and in contacting with people from outside the premises. The access to the community is convenient and there are various entrances. The attachment of the people to the Royal Guards Community in general and by each category is at a high level. The feeling that the community is their home rated the highest average. Factors that influence the attachment of the people of the Royal Guards Community are age, status, profession, income, length of stay in the community, membership of social groups, having neighbors they feel close and familiar with, and as well as the benefits they receive from the community. In addition, it was found that people that participate in activities have a high level of positive relationship towards the attachment of the people to the Royal Guards Community. The satisfaction of the community has a very high level of positive relationship with the attachment of the people to the Royal Guards Community.

The characteristics of the attachment of military families' is that they live in big houses that everyone has to protect and care for, starting from the leader of the family as well as all members. Therefore, they all love the community they live in. The characteristics that show the participation of activities within the community and the high level of satisfaction towards the premises of the community will enable the people to be more attached to the community. The people feel that everyone is close neighbors within the community, as if they are one big family.

Keywords—Activities, Attachment, Community, Royal Guards, Satisfaction.

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COUNTRIES are influenced by geography, culture, and customs. Geographical area is a main factor that determines the extinction of man or the development of families that later grow into communities. Overall, the influence of the community gets passed on from one generation to another. The conservation within the community becomes priceless local wisdom, with the development of a just society [1].

When the culture and customs change in a community; the economy is also affected. This is true when peoples' lives change by way of government's policies. Nevertheless, communities have a clear pattern that can be altered from various circumstances. This correlates with the perception of people toward the unity of an urban society that is not strongly tied. That is anyway, a hypothesis only. So the relationship of people toward community really requires many factors depending on the context of that society as well. For The Royal Guard Community of Dusit District, Bangkok Metropolitan, it belongs to soldiers who have carried on for many generations.

There are 290 houses which includes the house for Royal Soldiers called "Soldier Building". Everyone knows each other and shares their love and care harmoniously. This building provides more available space than the subornments. The size of these rooms is slightly bigger than a flat. Also there are townhomes for the elder soldiers who are retired. The characteristic of this community is comprised of soldiers and their families with an active relationship with Phomnapes Bunt and Phusit Phukamchanoad, which require full cooperation [2].

Leader of the community, General Giring Boontenom said, "Seventy percent of communities members are not Bangkokians, but they are Buddhists. Everyone participates in activities and live happily as one big family."

On August 12th, 2010, a new parliament was established on Kiakkai Soldier road, Dusit District [3].

Unfortunately, there were not clear instructions about expropriation for all residents during that time, and no immigration plans were made for them. This made people concerned and worried about residency. Sukanchana, a forty-four year old housewife said, "No sooner had all people become aware of the news, they couldn't even go to sleep as they had no place to live." They didn't expect anything more from the Saluk Neur Temple area as their salaries are very small.

Soldiers in Thailand have very low salaries; so finding satisfaction within their community seems more important to

share their wisdom and readily adjust themselves for the changing society [4].

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To Study and review the different levels of participation within the communities' activities. Study the relationship between people and community. Review factors of satisfaction and influence between the relationships of people.

III. METHODOLOGY

The sampling of this study is 287 people who live in Yankroa Community, Dusit District, Bangkok [5]. Data was used from questionnaires provided by these people who were eighteen or older; from these families. Also the samples included interviews with community leaders and their respectful elders; totaling twenty people.

The researcher analyzes data with Descriptive Statistics, Arithmetic Mean, standard Deviation, and Inferential Statistics; to compare and test those results namely; Independent-Samples T-test(T-test), one-way ANOVA(F-test).

For criteria of participation, it is an average between 3.01-4.00 in high level, and the average between 2.01-3.00 comes with a medium level, while the average between 1.00-2.00 shows lower a standard. About the satisfaction of people to community, the highest average is between 4.21-5.00, the high average is between 3.41-4.20, the medium average is between 2.61-3.40, the low medium average is between 2.60-1.80, and the lowest average is 1.80 [6].

The relationship of people toward The Royal Guard Community had a high average of 3.68-5.00, medium average of 2.34-36.7, and the low average is 1.00-2.33.

IV. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

A. Tables

People who live in The Royal Guard Community are members of soldier families and want to overall participate in activities within the community. With an average of 2.89, people are willing to join King and Queen's Birthday, which represented Father's Day and Mother's Day of the nation.

In relation to the satisfaction of peoples living areas; it showed 4.65 was the high average. The love average toward the community was 4.61. 4.69 were for the interaction with society, 4.67 was the relationship in duty.

The entity and identity of community showed 4.65. Overall, the people within the community were completely satisfied in all categories as shown in Tables I-III.

TABLE I
 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ROYAL GUARD AND COMMUNITY

Community attachment	Mean	S.D.	Interpretation
The attachment in place	4.67	0.43	High
The love toward community	4.69	0.45	High
The identity of community	4.65	0.47	High
The relationship in duty	4.66	0.47	High
The interaction with society	4.67	0.50	High
Love toward community like home	4.71	0.45	High
Total	4.61	0.37	High

TABLE II
 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE COMMUNITY AND DUSIT DISTRICT, BANGKOK

Feeling like home	Mean	S.D.	Interpretation
Feeling like home	4.67	0.52	High
Feeling safe	4.69	0.53	High
Felling free to share comments in activities	4.69	0.57	High
Feeling happy and freedom	4.72	0.51	High
Feeling free to talk with others like relatives	4.77	0.45	High
Total	4.71	0.45	High

TABLE III
 THE COMMUNITIES OVERALL SATISFACTION

Community satisfactions	Mean	S.D.	Interpretation
Area with enough area for people to live	4.70	0.50	High
Area with convenience to contact outsiders	4.64	0.55	High
Accessing to the community with various ways	4.71	0.57	High
Area with safety from thieves	4.62	0.57	High
Area without narcotic or drug	4.64	0.63	High
Occupations of people in the area	4.68	0.60	High
Transportation in the community or outside	4.71	0.57	High
Electricity Generation in the community	4.64	0.53	High
Water supply in the community	4.65	0.53	High
Telephone communication in the community	4.64	0.54	High
Health service in the community	4.64	0.54	High
Security in the community	4.68	0.52	High
Education in the community	4.68	0.57	High
Environment and lifestyles of people in the community	4.64	0.62	High
Sanitation and trash elimination	4.69	0.55	High
Shops and restaurants in the community	4.64	0.57	High
Employment center in the community	4.57	0.66	High
Structures of Buildings and houses in the community	4.65	0.53	High
Water pipe and elimination in the community	4.65	0.57	High
The green area for recreation	4.69	0.51	High
Total	4.65	0.45	High

B. Figures

The interview of community leaders and the elderly found that the relationship of people in the Royal Guard Community can be divided into three factors:

All people love and highly value their ancestry and family tradition; because they feel safe and proud to share their lives with their forefathers and feel right at home. This community is like a big family that allows everyone to share their love and respect for each other [7].

The people in this community believe in unity and co-operation among their community leaders. They protect their community [8].

Anyone over the Age of forty-one loved their community more than people younger than forty years old. Those older than twenty-one years old had more respect toward The Royal Guard Community than those younger than twenty years. The companionship within the community is shown in Figs. 1-3.

Fig. 1 Interview with a Community Leader

Fig. 2 The Royal Guard Community meeting

Fig. 3 Talking about Community satisfaction

V. DISCUSSION

The relationship within The Royal Guard Community is

shown with a high average of 4.61. Considering all factors, the feeling at home is 4.71; fondness for the community 4.69; concern with society is 4.67; pride of duty was 4.66 and finally, pride of entity is 4.65.

Most of the people have lived in this community for more than twenty years and feel they have great neighbors. They gain a lot of benefit from being members of this community in terms of transportation, and the health Center.

The most important thing that everyone agrees is this community is free from danger or potential threat. In a related interview, back in 2011; Jintana Bucha stated all housewives feel love for this community as their only home. The love toward the community is at an all time high which is about 75.4 percent [9], [10].

VI. CONCLUSION

A Community leader should consider the benefits of attachment one has to The Royal Guard Community. Due to the fact that the participation of people show a medium level with a low average, the leader must provide a place for people to have meetings, consult, and ask for feedback from the community. The community leader must also factor that employees of any private organization, may not always have time to participate with activities within the Royal Guard Community.

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